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A CRITICAL DISCOURSE ANALYSIS OF FEMINIST REPRESENTATION IN

GIWA'S *I'D RATHER DIE!*

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Abstract

In patriarchal societies, women are often represented as passive and powerless, a condition reinforced by socialisation processes that normalize male dominance and silence female voices. This study employs Norman Fairclough's three-dimensional model of CDA, which comprises textual analysis, discursive practice, and social practice in order to interrogate the representation of female characters in Audee T. Giwa's *I'd Rather Die!*. The data for the study were derived from selected excerpts within the novel that portray gendered interactions, with particular focus on the linguistic choices, narrative patterns, and ideological positions embedded in the text. The qualitative analytical method was adopted as a methodology and it involved detailed textual examination and interpretive analysis with a view to uncover the ideological implications of language use. The findings of the study reveal that while the female characters are initially depicted through conventional stereotypes of weakness and dependence, they progressively assert agency and self-determination, thereby subverting patriarchal constraints. The study thus concludes that Giwa's deliberate linguistic strategies empower his female characters, which enable them to reclaim their voices and challenge the dominance of male-centred discourse. This research contributes to the ongoing scholarly dialogue on gender representation, power relations, and discourse in African literary studies.

Keywords: Critical Discourse Analysis, feminism, gender, patriarchy, ideology.

Introduction

Language is far more than a vehicle of communication; it is a social instrument through which ideologies are constructed, legitimised and resisted. As a form of social practice, language reflects the structures of power and inequality that govern human interaction. Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA), as theorised by Fairclough (2013) and further advanced in recent scholarship (Adebayo, 2022; Wodak & Meyer, 2023), provides a theoretical and methodological framework for uncovering the ways in which discourse reproduces or challenges dominant social ideologies. Within this perspective, discourse is understood as both socially constitutive and socially conditioned, an arena where language both mirrors and transforms social realities.

In patriarchal societies, gender relations are shaped by deeply ingrained ideologies that privilege male authority while marginalising female agency. Such ideologies are often normalised through discourse that portrays women as passive, dependent, and subordinate to men. These representations, sustained by cultural narratives and linguistic practices, not only define the social positioning of women but also influence how they perceive themselves and their capacity for resistance. As scholars such as Makamani (2021) and Nyandoro (2024) note, discourse plays a central role in perpetuating gender inequality, yet it also provides a site for contestation and transformation.

Contemporary African scholarship on CDA and gender continues to reveal the complex interplay between language, power, and identity. According to Burr (2015) gender is socially constructed through discourse and language which shapes our understanding of masculinity and feminism. Siboro (2023) corroborates Burr (2015) and affirms the use of language to demonstrate gender ideology, and power is tightly tied to social attitudes. Language is used to construct gender by

emphasizing and conveying societal expectations for both sexes (Rahmi, 2015). Siboro (2023) reiterates that the societal perception of these distinct roles and behaviour patterns expected of men and women empowers some individuals while disempowering others. This explains why Audee uses language to reveal how some people such as Fatima are disempowered in the face of struggles and challenges.

Within this evolving discourse landscape, African literature remains a fertile site for examining how gender ideologies are represented and resisted. Literary narratives not only reflect prevailing social realities but also engage in the critique and reconstruction of those realities through language. Giwa's *I'd Rather Die!* exemplifies this intersection of discourse, ideology, and gender. The novel explicates the struggles of women who, though constrained by patriarchal expectations, navigate and resist the ideologies that seek to silence them. Through linguistic and narrative strategies, Giwa exposes the mechanisms of female subjugation while simultaneously empowering his female characters to reclaim agency and voice. This study, therefore, employs Fairclough's three-dimensional model of Critical Discourse Analysis, which comprise textual, discursive, and social practice with a view to interrogate the representation of women in *I'd Rather Die!*.

A synopsis of *I'd Rather Die!*

Audee's first novel which incidentally is the novel, *I'd Rather Die!*, was published in 1994. The novel recounts the story of Fatimah, a young girl "who takes anything that affects her life seriously". The manner Audee presents his characters in his novels resonates with so many people because they can see themselves in such struggles and circumstances, therefore, understand what the characters experience. Fatimah is a seventeen-year-old girl who has lived

with her family all through her young life and her father, a teacher who earns what can hardly sustain his family, mistreats the family due to the weight of supporting them. Fatimah is betrothed to Muhammed, a young undergraduate who is ready to give her equal opportunity to excel academically since it is her desire. Their hopes and aspirations are dashed when Fatima's father decides that Fatima must marry Alhaji Maikudi, a rich man, who is in search of a male child. Alhaji Maikudi relies on his money to get what he wants by being generous to Mallam Umar who starts to enjoy this largesse beyond his expectations. It is, therefore, not surprising that he considers Fatima a fair exchange for Alhaji Maikudi's benevolence. Fatima vehemently opposes her father's idea that she should marry Alhaji Maikudi and instead declares that she would rather die than marry him. The novel is so artistically rich in nature that it strikes a chord within its readers. The idea of the young Fatimah trying to exercise her right resonates with many people especially people who have been faced with similar fate.

CONCEPTUAL REVIEW

This section reviews concepts that are relevant to the study; thus, concepts such as Critical Discourse Analysis, Feminism, Gender and Discourse among other concepts, were reviewed.

Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA)

Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) is a multidisciplinary approach to studying language as a form of social practice that both reflects and shapes power relations in society. It views discourse not as neutral communication but as a site where ideology, dominance, and resistance are negotiated. According to Fairclough (2013), discourse operates on three interrelated levels: textual, discursive, and social practice, through which social meanings are constructed and reproduced. Wodak and Meyer (2023) emphasise that CDA seeks to reveal the implicit

ideologies encoded in linguistic structures, arguing that discourse is an instrument of both oppression and social change.

Recent scholarship has expanded the scope of CDA to include socio-cultural and gendered dimensions of discourse. For instance, Adebayo (2022) stresses that CDA provides critical insight into how everyday language perpetuates marginalisation through the normalisation of discriminatory ideologies. Similarly, Mungwini (2024) argues that CDA bridges linguistic and socio-political inquiry by exposing the unequal power dynamics that underpin both institutional and literary discourses. Thus, CDA offers not only a methodological tool but also an emancipatory framework for examining how texts contribute to maintaining or subverting social hierarchies. In literary analysis, CDA enables scholars to uncover how authors deploy language to resist dominant ideologies and to construct alternative identities, particularly for marginalised groups.

Feminism

Feminism is a socio-political and intellectual movement that challenges patriarchal structures and seeks gender equality across social, economic, and cultural spheres. From the perspective of Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA), feminism goes beyond advocacy to examine how language constructs, sustains, or resists gendered power relations. Language, as a social practice, embodies ideologies that shape and legitimise unequal gender positions within discourse (Fairclough, 1995). Feminist CDA investigates how textual and linguistic choices, such as agency, modality, and transitivity encode gender hierarchies or contest them within literary and social texts (Lazar, 2005).

Lazar (2005) identifies key principles of Feminist CDA, which include: (a) resistance to patriarchal ideologies, (b) recognition of gender as a discursively produced category, (c) awareness of the complexity and fluidity of power relations, and (d) the use of critical reflexivity to promote social transformation. Feminist CDA thus rejects the notion of neutrality, and view analysis as a means to expose and challenge the discursive reproduction of inequality.

Gender and Discourse

Gender, as a social construct, refers to the roles, expectations, and attributes assigned to individuals based on their perceived sex. It is sustained and reproduced through discourse, that is, through the habitual ways of speaking, writing, and representing men and women in social and cultural contexts. Butler's (1990) concept of gender performativity remains central to understanding how language and social practice continually construct gendered identities. More recent studies have emphasised the discursive reproduction of gender hierarchies in African contexts. Makamani (2021) observes that patriarchal ideology in African societies is largely discursive, transmitted through proverbs, idioms, and narrative forms that depict women as subordinate. Similarly, Nyandoro (2024) explores how everyday discourse reinforces male dominance through linguistic exclusion and evaluative bias.

Gender discourse analysis thus examines how texts- whether literary, political, or media-based, construct women's subjectivity and define their place within social hierarchies. Through CDA, researchers can identify the subtle ways in which language not only reflects gender imbalance but also provides opportunities for resistance and redefinition. In Giwa's *I'd Rather Die!*, for instance, female characters are linguistically represented as struggling against culturally sanctioned silence. Through CDA, this study interrogates how Giwa's linguistic choices

challenge these socially constructed gender norms and empower his female characters to renegotiate their identities.

Patriarchy and Power Relations

Patriarchy refers to a social and ideological system in which men hold power and authority over women in political, social, and domestic spheres. It is maintained not only through institutional structures, but also through cultural and linguistic mechanisms that normalise male dominance. As noted by Tamale (2022), patriarchy persists in African societies through discursive practices that equate masculinity with authority and femininity with submission. Such power asymmetries are reflected in both social discourse and literary expression, where female experiences are often marginalised or portrayed as secondary to male narratives.

Critical scholars such as Chilwa and Odebunmi (2023) emphasise that discourse plays a pivotal role in sustaining patriarchal ideology by positioning women within limited representational frames, such as the obedient wife or the self-sacrificing mother. However, feminist CDA perspectives argue that the same discourse can serve as a medium of resistance. By re-appropriating language, women writers and characters can challenge the ideological assumptions that underpin patriarchy. Giwa's *I'd Rather Die!* exemplifies this process, as his female characters use language and narrative to confront, reinterpret, and subvert patriarchal authority.

Ideology and Representation

Ideology, in the context of discourse studies, refers to the system of beliefs, values, and assumptions that shape and justify social practices and relations of power. Fairclough (2013) and Van Dijk (2020) contend that ideologies are embedded in discourse through lexical choices, thematic structures, and narrative framing. These ideologies are often invisible yet powerful,

shaping how readers perceive social reality. In literary discourse, ideology operates through representation of the ways in which authors depict characters, events, and social relations in ways that either reinforce or question dominant worldviews.

Recent CDA research (e.g., Lazar, 2021; Alghamdi, 2023) demonstrates that literary texts often encode ideologies of gender, class, and power through subtle linguistic cues. However, literature also functions as a counter-hegemonic space where marginalised voices contest dominant ideologies. Within the text, *I'd Rather Die!*, ideological representation manifests through the struggle between silence and speech, submission and defiance. Giwa's narrative strategy reflects an ideological repositioning of women from passive recipients of oppression to active agents of resistance, thus redefining their social identity within a patriarchal order.

Empirical Studies

Several works have been done on Giwa's novels; Ahmed (2010) interrogated the northern Nigerian society in Giwa's *I'd Rather Die!* and *With Love From Fatika*. The researcher explores gender and sexuality. The study explores the author's immediate society and interrogates the characters based on the northern Nigerian society. The researcher adopted the feminist theory as her analytical tool. The study finds out that immorality and greed are prevalent in the society and suggests that society should adopt a pragmatic approach in addressing the issue. The study is similar to the current study in the sense that the same text is analysed but differs in the theoretical approach. The current study applies the critical discourse analysis to interrogate male dominance which is a prevalent theme.

Babajo and Ijaoba (2020) also undertook a study of Giwa's novels and submit that Giwa portrays the women in his novels as characters in real life. The study adopts the Womanism approach as

the theoretical framework which is different from the one adopted by the current study. Even though the two works are on *I'd Rather Die!*, the difference in theoretical approaches set them apart. Babajo and Ijaoba (2020) reveal that the author has great insight and deep feelings for his female characters, empathises with them, and shows that they are able to stand up to their oppressors. Babajo and Ijaoba (2020) conclude that Giwa has a clear perspective of his female characters and depicts them as confident and diplomatic people. Babajo and Ijaoba (2020) note that Giwa presents his character as people who are not weak, voiceless or vulnerable; as a matter of fact, he has given them a voice; and equipped them with self-worth and self-identity to survive in an aggressive world.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on Norman Fairclough's (1992, 2013) Three-Dimensional Model of Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA), which conceptualises discourse as a form of social practice that both reflects and shapes power relations within society. Fairclough's model provides a comprehensive framework for analysing how language is used to construct ideology, sustain dominance, or promote resistance.

The framework consists of three interrelated dimensions: the textual, the discursive practice, and the social practice. The textual dimension focuses on the linguistic properties of texts, vocabulary, grammar, cohesion, and rhetorical structures, through which ideology and identity are encoded. The discursive practice dimension examines the processes of text production, distribution, and interpretation, emphasising intertextuality and interdiscursivity as means through which texts derive meaning within social contexts. The social practice dimension situates discourse within broader socio-cultural and ideological structures, interrogating how

language reproduces or challenges social inequality and dominance, as highlighted by Van Dijk (2020) and Wodak and Meyer (2023).

This framework is particularly suitable for the present study because it integrates linguistic, social, and ideological analysis, enabling a holistic exploration of how Giwa's *I'd Rather Die!*, constructs gendered power relations and female resistance through language. The application of Fairclough's model for this study helps to uncover how discourse functions not only as a reflection of patriarchy but also as a tool for its contestation and transformation.

Methodology

This study adopts primary and the secondary sources of data. The primary source is the text, *I'd Rather Die!*, while the secondary sources of data include scholarly journals and other textual materials. The data for analysis were sourced from *I'd Rather Die!* which is the primary text. The data were purposively selected because they fit into Fairclough's analytical framework which has three dimensions: textual analysis, discursive analysis and social analysis. The immediate condition, from which a text is evolved, is important for the authentic interpretation of the text. Thus, the analysis focuses on the language and individual words that shape a text which is the very first analytical attention of Fairclough's model. According to Fairclough (1995, p.57), "Linguistic analysis includes the analysis of the grammar, vocabulary, sound system, semantics, cohesion and organisation above the sentence level." All the descriptions of grammar are based on text. When people speak or write, they produce text with which readers and listeners engage and interpret. So, text is a process of making meaning in context.

The paper thus adopts a qualitative descriptive approach and considers the textual and social analysis which shows the linguistic descriptions of the formal properties of the text as well as the social analysis as suitable analytical tools.

Data Presentation and Analysis

This section presents and analyses the data collected for the study. The data for this study was presented and analysed using Fairclough's three-dimensional model of Critical Discourse Analysis which comprise textual, discursive, and social practice.

Textual Analysis

According to Fairclough (1995, 2013), the textual level of analysis involves the linguistic examination of vocabulary, grammar, transitivity, modality, and cohesion to uncover the ideological meanings embedded in discourse. Through these linguistic choices, the author encodes attitudes, power relations, and identity constructions.

Vocabulary

Fairclough (1995) argues that over wording, which is the excessive use of particular lexical items, often signals ideological struggle. In *I'd Rather Die!*, lexical choices such as "anger", "threatening", and "blazing rage" highlight the intensity of male authority and emotional dominance, as seen in the excerpt below:

"He stared at her in anger." (p.8)

"He stood up threateningly; he stood up in a blazing rage." (p.9)

"He blundered into the room." (p. 9)

The underlined words portray Mal. Umar as an aggressive patriarch, reinforcing a discourse of male control and female subordination. His wife's silence and restricted agency signify how language mirrors gender hierarchy. The words "anger", "threateningly" and "blazing rage" are emotions targeted at his wife.

Similarly, Fatima's recurrent use of the expression "*I'd rather die!*", shows her struggle and unwillingness to accept her father's choice of a husband, as evident in the following excerpt:

"No! I won't marry him father! I would rather leave this house and go to any whore-house in town. Or better still, I'd rather die!" (p. 91).

In p. 37, Fatima's use of the expression "I'd rather die" while speaking with Mahmud is different from the tone she used when she equally expressed the same sentiment in p. 91. Fatima vehemently declares that she will not marry Alhaji Maikudi. The excerpt above is meant to register her dismay and rebellion, as she decides to break away from the cast of being a victim to taking charge of her life. The word "house" reoccurs in the two instances when she mentioned that she would rather die. Ideally, the word "house" connotes warmth, family and all that is comfortable but she was ready to give it up in order to exert her desire for freedom. The stronger expression, "I'd rather die", implies that she was courageous and had the conviction to do what she knew was important to her - her right to choose her own husband by herself.

Tense and Transitivity

"I have been seeing you for quite a long time, but I kept telling myself there was no harm in loving somebody". (p. 51)

The above excerpt indicates the use of both present perfect continuous and past continuous tenses to express persistence and emotional continuity. The use of “have been seeing” indicates an ongoing action that began in the past and extends into the present, which reflect Mohammed’s sustained affection for Fatima. Conversely, “kept telling myself” captures a habitual past action, which shows his repeated internal struggle to rationalise his feelings. From Fairclough’s (1995) perspective, these tense choices go beyond grammatical expression; they reveal how the speaker constructs his identity as a patient, and emotionally stable figure. In addition, it reveals that he is able to negotiate his desire within social and moral constraints.

In terms of transitivity, the clause structure primarily reflects mental and relational processes, which illustrate Mohammed’s internal reflections rather than external actions. Phrases such as: “I have been seeing you” and “I kept telling myself” exemplify mental processes which involve perception and cognition, where ‘I’ serves as the *Senser*, and ‘you’ or ‘myself’ as the *Phenomenon*. Similarly, “there was no harm in loving somebody” represents a relational process, which express evaluation and moral reasoning. Through these linguistic choices, Mohammed’s discourse is framed as self-reflective and emotionally introspective, which aligns with Fairclough’s (1995) view that transitivity patterns encode how individuals experience and interpret social reality.

Mood/Modality

“Fatima ...was deprived of the right to further her education by her frugal father” (p. 16).

The above excerpt reflects a discourse of power and gender inequality. The declarative mood presents Fatima’s deprivation as a factual event, which normalises patriarchal control and

silences her agency. By casting Fatima as the affected participant and her father as the actor, the sentence encodes an unequal power relation that mirrors societal patriarchy. The modality in “Mal. Umar was presented as a teacher, but the contrary is the case” (p. 16) conveys moral judgment and ideological critique, exposing the contradiction between his professional identity and his oppressive action. Thus, through mood and modality, the text simultaneously reveals and challenges the patriarchal ideology that denies women access to education.

Social Analysis

At the level of social practice, the author reveals the deep-rooted gender bias and patriarchal ideology that seems to structure the characters’ experiences. The portrayal of Fatima’s despair and helplessness in the novel has foregrounded the social consequences of unequal gender relations and the oppressive expectations imposed on women. Fatima’s decision to prefer death over an unwanted marriage reflects the extreme emotional and psychological burden produced by a society that prioritises obedience and family honour over women’s autonomy. In Fairclough’s (1995) terms, the social dimension of discourse connects textual choices to broader ideological and institutional practices, where cultural system legitimises male dominance and restricts female agency.

Representation of Women

Excerpt 1:

Mal Umar: “What the hell have you been doing in the house?”

“You have been sleeping.” “Ah, well done, Queen Amina of Zazzau”. (p. 9)

Excerpt 2:

Mal Umar: “Do I have to ask for my food?” (p.10)

Excerpts 1 and 2 illustrate how women are positioned and perceived within a patriarchal social structure. The discourse reflects gendered power asymmetry, where women are portrayed as dependent and incapable of making autonomous decisions without male supervision. The male character, Mal. Umar, embodies this dominance, where he views the women in his household as personal property rather than as individuals with self-determination. His anger toward his wife, questioning what she does all day and denying her right to rest, reinforces a discourse of subjugation in which domestic labour is undervalued and female effort is rendered invisible. The rhetorical question, “Do I have to ask for my food?” encapsulates his sense of entitlement and authority, which simply implies that his wife exists solely to serve him. Through such linguistic and behavioural expressions, the text exposes how everyday interactions reproduce ideological control and gender inequality.

Beauty Myth

“There are few women who are described as pretty as well as beautiful. Fatima was among the lucky few. Her nicely rounded face was as smooth as velvet and as soft. If the sight of her didn’t make an imam miss a line in his recitation, it would definitely make him clear his voice in appreciation.” (p.14)

The above excerpt foregrounds the representation of women through the discourse of beauty and sexuality, which reflects the gendered ideology that objectifies women within patriarchal societies. The description of Fatima’s physical appearance as, “Her nicely rounded face was as smooth as velvet” (p.14) constructs femininity through the lens of physical appearance rather than intellect or agency. In Fairclough’s CDA framework, such linguistic representation

operates ideologically to reproduce social perceptions that equate a woman's value with her attractiveness.

Giwa's narrative maintains this stereotypical dichotomy in which inner strength is coded as masculine while beauty defines femininity. The recurrent emphasis on Fatima's physical appeal, as further echoed in Alhaji Maikudi's comment "A paragon of beauty and has got eyes that made me forget I am old" (p. 75) reinforces the beauty myth that confines women to the role of aesthetic admiration and erotic objectification. Through these portrayals, the novel mirrors societal discourses where female worth is measured by desirability, which naturalises gender inequality. The analysis thus reveals how language in this text both reflects and sustains the patriarchal ideology embedded in everyday social relations.

Social and Physical Oppression

In the novel, Giwa exposes the social and psychological oppression of women through patriarchal control embedded in language and social relations. Fatima's forced marriage decision, imposed by her father without regard for her emotions, exemplifies ideological domination where male authority dictates female destiny. This reflects Fairclough's view of discourse as a means of power reproduction, using everyday interactions to naturalise unequal gender roles.

Similarly, Zainab's experience mirrors this discursive subjugation. Although "Zainab feared her parents very much" her coerced marriage to Alhaji Maikudi reveals how family and societal norms perpetuate women's silence and compliance. Alhaji's intention to "beat the hell out of her" illustrates both physical and symbolic violence, which reinforces the patriarchal ideology

that legitimises male dominance. Zainab's defiance and eventual respect from her co-wives disrupt this power order, thereby demonstrating resistance within discourse.

Self-Identity

The author in this novel presents self-identity as a gradual process of self-awareness shaped by emotional and social experiences. Self-identity, as the recognition of one's distinct self within a social context, becomes evident in Fatima's emotional awakening: "She felt her heart skip a beat the moment their eyes locked" (p.17). This moment signifies her emerging consciousness of self, which marks the transition from innocence to emotional awareness.

The application of Fairclough's CDA explores Fatima's evolving identity which reflects the intersection of individual psychology and social ideology. While love becomes a site of self-discovery, it also exposes her vulnerability within a patriarchal society that limits female expression. Unlike the conventional portrayal of women's insecurities rooted in physical appearance, Fatima's self-doubt is psychological, tied to uncertainty about her emotions and societal expectations of obedience and restraint. Thus, Giwa uses Fatima's internal conflict to critique how social discourse shapes personal identity, thereby revealing how self-awareness in women often emerges through resistance to restrictive cultural norms.

Conclusion

Through the application of Fairclough's social analysis, it becomes evident that the female characters in Giwa's *I'd Rather Die!* are consistently subjugated within a male-dominated social structure. The novel exposes the subtle and overt mechanisms through which patriarchy sustains its power, through language, ideology, and social expectations. Such sexist representations demand critical attention in literary discourse, as they reflect and reinforce real-world gender hierarchies. When narratives that normalise female oppression are repeatedly told and consumed without critique, society risks becoming desensitised to sexism, which will portray its acceptance as a natural order. Therefore, exposing and interrogating these gendered discourses is essential not only for literary analysis but also for challenging the patriarchal ideologies that literature both mirrors and shapes.

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